

PECULIARITIES OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY

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International law is an important tool for achieving gender equality globally, offering a framework to guide states in promoting and protecting the rights of women and girls. What makes international law unique in this direction is its specific features and approaches. First, international law provides a universal standard of gender equality. It transcends national and cultural boundaries and establishes basic principles and norms that apply regardless of the individual legal systems of all countries. This universality emphasizes the principle that gender equality is not only a domestic concern, but a shared responsibility of the international community¹. Second, international law comprehensively addresses gender equality in various areas of human life. From political participation to economic empowerment, education, health and protection from violence, international legal instruments cover a wide range of issues related to the achievement of gender equality². This comprehensive approach reflects the multifaceted nature of gender discrimination and emphasizes the need for comprehensive strategies to effectively address it³.

Furthermore, international law recognizes the intersection of gender with other identities and experiences. It recognizes that individuals may face different forms of discrimination based on factors such as race, ethnicity, religion, disability, sexual orientation or socioeconomic status. International law seeks to address the unique challenges and vulnerabilities faced by diverse groups of women and girls, ensuring that efforts to achieve gender equality are inclusive and equitable. International law also provides accountability and enforcement mechanisms. Through treaty bodies, international courts and monitoring mechanisms, states are responsible for their obligations to ensure gender equality within the framework of international law⁴. These mechanisms allow individuals and groups to seek redress for violations of their rights and ensure that states take concrete steps to address gender-based discrimination

¹ The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), adopted in 1979.

² UN Women - CEDAW [UN Women, CEDAW], OHCHR - Human Rights Treaties [OHCHR, Human Rights Treaties].

³ UN Women - Gender Equality and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

⁴ The International Court of Justice (ICJ) can hear disputes between states regarding human rights violations, including gender equality. While not specifically focused on gender equality, some cases heard by the ICJ have touched on this aspect ([ICJ], [University of Minnesota Human Rights Center, International Courts and Tribunals]).

and inequality. International law strengthens cooperation and solidarity among states, organizations and civil society actors in promoting gender equality. Through conventions, resolutions and international conferences, stakeholders share best practices and coordinate efforts to ensure gender equality at the global, regional and national levels⁵. This collaborative approach enhances the impact of individual initiatives and facilitates collective action towards common goals.

The distinctive features of international law in ensuring gender equality are its universality, comprehensiveness, interdependence, responsibility and ability to develop cooperation. Using these features, international law serves as a powerful tool to advance the rights and interests of women and girls around the world, contributing to a more just, inclusive and equal world for all⁶. International law recognizes the importance of gender mainstreaming in decision-making processes at all levels. This includes not only ensuring equal representation of women in the political and public spheres, but also integrating gender analysis into policy formulation, implementation and evaluation. By mainstreaming gender issues in governance structures and practices, international law seeks to remove systemic barriers to gender equality and develop more inclusive and responsive governance systems.

Already, international law can help empower women and girls as active agents of change in their rights. International legal instruments seek to expand their voices and perspectives in shaping policies and programs that affect their lives, while recognizing⁷ their rights to participate, lead and make decisions. Such empowerment not only contributes to more effective and sustainable development outcomes, but also empowers women and girls to realize their full potential and contribute to society. will shoot. International law fosters a culture of accountability and transparency in combating gender-based violence and discrimination. Through mechanisms such as reporting obligations, monitoring frameworks and accountability mechanisms, states are held accountable for their actions or inactions in addressing gender-based human rights violations. It helps build a culture of respect for women's rights and ensures that perpetrators

⁵ The UN Commission on the Status of Women (CSW).

⁶ While international law offers a powerful framework, enforcement and implementation can be uneven across countries. Civil society plays a crucial role in holding governments accountable [UN Women, Implementation of International Agreements].

⁷ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights enshrines the right to freedom of expression and participation in government (Articles 19 and 21) [UN Human Rights Office, Universal Declaration of Human Rights].

of violence are held accountable for their actions, and survivors have access to justice, reparations and support services⁸.

Simply put, the distinctive features of international law in promoting gender equality lie in its ability to integrate gender perspectives into decision-making, promote transnational cooperation, empower women and girls, and promote accountability for gender-based violations. By leveraging these unique features, international law serves as a powerful tool for promoting gender equality and realizing the rights and aspirations of women and girls worldwide.

International legal instruments recognize the importance of addressing the historical injustices and systemic inequalities that perpetuate gender-based discrimination. Through mechanisms such as transitional justice processes and reparations programs, international legal frameworks seek to redress⁹ past harms to women and girls, including those caused by conflict, colonialism or systemic discrimination. By recognizing and challenging these injustices, international law contributes to processes of healing and reconciliation, laying the groundwork for building more inclusive and just societies.

In particular, international law supports cross-sectoral cooperation and partnerships to promote gender equality. International legal frameworks facilitate multi-stakeholder initiatives and partnerships, recognizing that achieving gender equality requires the involvement of various stakeholders, including governments, civil society, the private sector and international organizations. These partnerships leverage resources, expertise and networks to implement gender-responsive policies and programs that address the root causes of gender inequality and promote transformative change. International law emphasizes the importance of data collection, research and evidence-based policy-making in promoting gender equality. By collecting reliable data and conducting gender analysis, international legal frameworks enable policymakers to understand the gender dimensions of various issues and develop targeted interventions that address the specific needs and priorities of women and girls¹⁰. This evidence-based approach ensures that policies and programs are based on empirical evidence and have a meaningful impact on gender equality

⁸ Treaties like CEDAW establish a global baseline for how women should be treated, fostering a shift in attitudes. ([UN Women, CEDAW]).

⁹ The UN Transitional Justice Framework emphasizes the importance of integrating gender perspectives into transitional justice processes, ensuring women's voices are heard and specific needs are addressed ([UN Office of the Special Adviser on the Prevention of Genocide and the Responsibility to Protect, The UN Transitional Justice Framework]).

¹⁰ International agreements often encourage the development of national action plans on gender equality. These plans rely on data collection and analysis to identify priority areas and target interventions. ([UN Women, National Action Plans on Women, Peace and Security]).

outcomes. Finally, international law recognizes the dynamic nature of gender relations and the need for constant adaptation and innovation in achieving gender equality. Through mechanisms such as regular review processes, capacity-building initiatives and knowledge-sharing platforms, international legal frameworks support continuous learning and improvement of gender mainstreaming efforts. It enables countries to stay abreast of emerging challenges and opportunities and adjust their strategies and approaches accordingly, so they can be relevant and effective in promoting gender equality in a rapidly changing world. ensures that it remains.

International law recognizes the importance of promoting gender-responsive approaches to peace-building and conflict resolution. In conflict, women and girls are often at risk of violence, injustice and disenfranchisement. International legal frameworks, such as UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security, emphasize the important role of women in peace-building processes and recognize their role in conflict prevention, resolution and decision-making at all stages thereafter. calls for meaningful participation ¹¹. conflict reconstruction. By ensuring that women's perspectives and priorities are integrated into peacebuilding efforts, international law promotes more sustainable and inclusive peace agreements that address the root causes of conflict and contribute to long-term stability.

Comprehensive legal protection against gender-based violence and discrimination is needed in many developing countries. Despite progress in recognizing and addressing these issues, many women and girls around the world continue to face widespread forms of violence and discrimination in their daily lives. Legal frameworks that criminalize gender-based violence, ensure access to justice and support services for survivors, and encourage prevention measures and awareness-raising campaigns are essential in combating human rights violations. By enshrining these protections into law and ensuring their effective implementation, international law contributes to a safer and more equitable environment for women and girls to live, work and thrive.

References:

1. International human rights law based on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted on December 10, 1948.
2. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) adopted in 1979.

¹¹ UNSCR 1325 calls for the increased participation of women in all stages of peace processes, including conflict prevention, resolution, peacekeeping, and post-conflict reconstruction. It emphasizes the importance of including women in decision-making at all levels. ([UN Women, Women, Peace and Security]).

3. The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, adopted at the Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995.
4. United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) - Adopted in 2000.
5. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).